

CRITICAL RATIONALISM AS A THEORY OF LEARNING: AN ETHICAL ANALYSIS

Azamatova Gulrukh Islom qizi

PhD student of the National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek

g.azamatova@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

In this article, the author explores the essence of critical rationalism as a learning theory. By analyzing the theories of learning developed within the fields of philosophy, pedagogy, and psychology, the author highlights their advantages and drawbacks from various perspectives. Based on this analysis, the author argues that modern education is based on an interdisciplinary approach, incorporating aspects from philosophy, pedagogy, psychology, and other social and humanities disciplines. The author then discusses the main aspects of critical rationalism as a modern learning theory. Through a broader examination of its application in education, the author focuses on the personal aspects of learning and subjects them to ethical and philosophical analysis. The author concludes by exploring the deep connection between critical rationalism and the formation of a person's personality, their upbringing, and further development. In this context, we see that ethical concepts such as freedom, individuality, and responsibility are essential, but knowledge, learning, teaching methods, and techniques are not fixed, but can change as society develops.

Keywords: education, pedagogy, teaching, ethics, critical rationalism, falsificationism, fallibilism, historicism.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье автор рассматривает сущность критического рационализма как теории обучения. Анализируя теории обучения, сложившиеся в рамках философии, педагогики и психологии, автор обращает внимание на их достоинства и недостатки с различных точек зрения. На основе этого анализа автор ставит цель показать, что современное образование и теория обучения основываются на междисциплинарности, вбирая в себя различные аспекты философии, педагогики, психологии и других социально-гуманитарных наук. Базируясь на этом, автор раскрывает основные аспекты критического рационализма как теории обучения в современную эпоху. Показывая более широкие моменты критического рационализма в его приложении к образованию, автор делает акцент и на частные аспекты обучения. Подвергая их

этико-философскому анализу, автор выводит глубокую взаимосвязь критического рационализма с обучением личности, ее воспитанием и дальнейшим развитием. В этом контексте показывается, что императивный характер носят такие этические понятия, как свобода, индивидуальность и ответственность, однако само знание, обучение, методики и техники обучения не являются окончательными, а могут подвергаться различным изменениям в связи с развитием общества.

Ключевые слова: образование, педагогика, обучение, этика, критический рационализм, фальсификационизм, фаллибилизм, историцизм.

ANNOTATSIYA

Mazkur maqolada muallif tanqidiy ratsionalizmning ta'lim nazariyasi sifatidagi mazmun-mohiyatini o'rganib chiqqan. Falsafa, pedagogika va psixologiya kabi fanlar doirasida shakllangan turli ta'lim nazariyalarini tahlili asosida muallif ularning afzalliklari hamda kamchiliklariga e'tibor qaratgan. Ushbu tahlil asosida muallif zamonaviy ta'lim va ta'lim nazariyasi falsafa, pedagogika, psixologiya va boshqa ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlarni o'z ichiga oladigan fanlararo yondashuvga asoslanganligini ko'rsatish maqsadini belgilagan. Buning asosida muallif tanqidiy ratsionalizmning zamonaviy davr ta'lim nazariyasi sifatidagi asosiy jihatlarini ochib bergan. Tanqidiy ratsionalizmning ta'limga nisbatan keng ma'nodagi asosiy tomonlarini ko'rsatib, muallif ta'limning aniq tomonlariga ham urg'u bergan va ularning falsafiy-axloqiy tahlili asosida tanqidiy ratsionalizmning insonni o'qitish, uni tarbiyalash va kelgusidagi taraqqiyoti bilan bog'liq chuqur aloqani ko'rsatmoqda. Mazkur kontekstda erkinlik, individuallik va mas'uliyat kabi axloqiy tushunchalar imperativ xarakterga egaligi hamda bilim, o'qitish, ta'lim metodikasi va texnikalari yakuniy xarakter ega emasligi, ular jamiyat rivoji bilan bog'liqlikda o'zgartirilishi mumkinligi ko'rsatilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'lim, pedagogika, o'qitish, etika, tandiqiy ratsionalizm, falsifikatsionizm, fallibilizm, tarixchilik.

In the modern philosophy of education, there are various theories of learning that are at the intersection of the philosophy of education itself, pedagogy, and psychology. Based on research into human behavior in the 20th century, *behaviorism* emerged, which found its way into pedagogy. Behaviorism is founded on the teachings of J. Watson, who says that the basis of the learning process is a stimulus-response relationship, as a result of which the entire learning process was determined to be based on stimulating specific behaviors in order to achieve learning goals [1,

51]. However, behaviorism denies all intellectual processes, as what happens inside a person's mind cannot be directly observed, unlike behavior. *Cognitivism*, on the other hand, is a learning theory that is in contrast to behaviorism. Cognitivism emphasizes intelligence and cognitive processes, and attempts to understand how individuals perceive learning, remember information, and process it. However, one significant drawback of this learning theory is its disregard for the socio-cultural context and limited consideration of emotions and motivation [1, 68-69]. A unique synthesis of behaviorism and cognitivism occurs in *social constructivism*. This approach believes that learning takes place in relation to the socio-cultural environment, as knowledge is a product of society [1, 77]. Learning in social constructivism also considers the values and beliefs of a society, which is not the case in behaviorism and cognitivism. Social constructivism, which considers learning to take place in a socio-cultural context, shows that learning is a process of assimilating values, morals, and ethics. However, social constructivist approaches do not emphasize the development of critical thinking skills, which can be a significant disadvantage. This lack of emphasis on critical analysis can lead to a lack of systematic thinking in the organization of the educational process. Educational practices within social constructivism may not be based on a strict curriculum, which can also contribute to this problem.

It is important to note that the theories discussed above are based on pedagogy and psychology. However, in the 20th century, new theories of learning emerged, which are rooted in various philosophical concepts. One such theory is *existentialism*, which is a holistic approach to learning. Existentialism emphasizes the importance of the individual student's experience and freedom, as well as their responsibility and authenticity [2, 90]. This philosophical approach has an ethical component that focuses on the fundamental ethical questions of research, such as freedom, responsibility, and authenticity. However, existentialism does not delve deeply into the cognitive aspects of education or pay sufficient attention to historical and cultural factors. Therefore, it is important to consider other theories and approaches to ensure a more comprehensive understanding of the learning process. From a philosophical perspective, this is of great significance, as it is necessary to integrate the national education system with the global educational landscape. A socio-philosophical analysis is required to identify the values of society, as outlined in [3, 160]. All these points are reflected in the *critical rationalism of Karl Popper*, which can be considered an independent theory of learning today.

It is known that Karl Popper's philosophy is based on the principles of falsificationism, critical rationalism, and an evolutionary view of the development of

science and society [4, 293]. Critical rationalism occupies a central position in Popper's thought, as it aims to critically analyze experience, not only scientific but also socio-cultural and ethical. Popper's approach seeks to challenge «authorities» [5, 55], as he believes that they are often wrong and need to be questioned. To understand the essence of Popper's critical rationalism, we must turn to his famous works such as «The Open Society and Its Enemies» and «Poverty of Historicism». In «The Open Society», Popper criticizes totalitarian concepts of society and proposes an alternative model based on freedom and individualism. In such a society, freedom has an important ethical significance. It becomes an indestructible imperative that ensures sustainable development [6]. Popper approaches this issue by criticizing not only totalitarian concepts but also historicism, as seen in his work «The Poverty of Historicism» [7]. He argues that there is no single direction or pattern of development. Everything happens through trial and error, and the historical process cannot be predicted or explained by certain determinants. Therefore, social science should abandon *providentialism* and focus on a critical rationalistic approach to science. This approach can offer conceptual approaches to social issues based on scientific principles [8, 1673]. That is, critical rationalism aims to falsify social experience and form new theories of social development based on this. However, how is critical rationalism applied as a theory of learning?

Karl Popper considered education as an essential foundation for social transformation. He also emphasized the importance of a critical approach to education, as certain educational practices may not be definitively true from a *fallibilist perspective*. As a result, approaches and teaching methods must be adapted and changed. In critical rationalism, the methodological basis for learning is based on the idea that social development is constantly evolving and undergoing various transformations. This emphasizes the need for continuous renewal and radical transformation in learning. Modern education is characterized by constant change in approaches to learning. The advent of *artificial intelligence* has led to the development of new techniques based on its applications [9, 55]. These techniques are already being used in education and research, and they will continue to evolve in the near future. Artificial intelligence will play a significant role in shaping educational and research practices [10]. In a more general sense, we can see that critical rationalism plays a significant role in the fundamental transformation of education in response to the social changes of our time. From a more specific perspective, critical rationalism emphasizes the development of *critical thinking* skills in students. This approach encourages students to analyze information, formulate hypotheses, ask questions, and critically evaluate different points of view.

Another important aspect of critical rationalism is the *acceptance of uncertainty and openness*. Given the sociocultural context, it is impossible to predict certain events with certainty. Therefore, learning should focus on fostering an openness to new ideas and an understanding that all *knowledge is provisional and probabilistic*. Students should also be taught how to adapt to changing information and adjust their views based on new evidence. However, all this requires an *empirical approach* to learning, as education should be based on concrete examples and experience. From the standpoint of critical rationalism, students should be given the opportunity to conduct observations, experiments, and research in order to formulate and test hypotheses. This also develops the skills of research activities from the school level onwards. In addition, critical rationalism pays attention to socio-cultural aspects and *stimulating discussion and debate* occupy a special place in this approach. Critical rationalists support active discussions and debates in the classroom, where students can argue their positions and listen to and analyze alternative viewpoints, coming to informed conclusions together. Students are taught to respect different opinions and criticize, as criticism should not be seen as a threat but as an opportunity for improvement. Another important aspect of critical rationalism is the emphasis on *independent learning*. This is because in order for individuals to develop in an open and evolving environment, it is essential to stimulate independent thought. This means that students should be given opportunities to explore topics that interest them and develop their own ideas and theories.

So, the key aspects of critical rationalism as a theory of learning include:

- formation and development of critical thinking;
- openness to and acceptance of uncertainty;
- empirical orientation;
- stimulating discussion and debate, respecting different opinions and criticisms;
- motivation for self-study.

In the context of the key aspects of critical rationalism mentioned above, we can see that the foundation of this philosophy is the fundamental concept of freedom. Students are taught to respect the *freedom* of others, while also maintaining their own *individuality*. Criticism should be constructive and rationally justified, avoiding personal attacks on others. Constructive criticism is only possible when it is based on *empirical evidence*, making the information more reliable. From an ethical perspective, the concept of *truth* is important in decision-making. The emphasis on independent learning fosters a *sense of responsibility*, which is essential, as freedom

and responsibility go hand in hand. From an ethical perspective, this outlines the main principles of *critical rationalism as a learning theory* in the modern age.

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